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The Serpent and the Sword: Erotic and Phallic Symbolism in Shakespeare's *Antony and Cleopatra*

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Abstract:

William Shakespeare's *Antony and Cleopatra* dramatise the collapse of Roman identity under the weight of passion and desire. Central to this conflict is Shakespeare's use of erotic and phallic imagery, which highlights the tension between sexuality and politics, personal identity and cultural duty. Cleopatra, through her beauty and erotic power, challenges patriarchal norms and undermines Antony's Roman masculinity. Swords and other phallic symbols emphasise the Roman ideal of manhood, yet Cleopatra subverts and reclaims them. Yonic symbols and fertility imagery connect Cleopatra to Egypt's abundance. The play also presents complex psycho-sexual dynamics, including sadism and masochism. This paper argues that Shakespeare uses erotic and phallic symbolism not only to depict the love affair between Antony and Cleopatra but also to question rigid gender roles, highlight cultural anxieties and dramatise the tragic consequences when desire collides with duty.

Keywords: Masochism, Erotic, Phallic Imagery, Cultural Anxieties, Sexuality.

Introduction

William Shakespeare's *Antony and Cleopatra* stand as one of his most ambitious plays, combining history, politics and romance with profound symbolic meaning. It is set against the backdrop of the Roman Empire's struggle for dominance. The play dramatises the love affair between Mark Antony, one of Rome's triumvirs and Cleopatra, the Queen of Egypt. More than a love story, it is a meditation on power, identity and cultural difference.

The central conflict of the play arises from the clash between Rome and Egypt. Rome is represented as masculine, rigid, disciplined and oriented toward the honour of the empire. Egypt, by contrast, is feminine, fluid, indulgent and linked with pleasure, luxury and desire. Antony, once a "fierce and feared general," becomes torn between his Roman duty and his Egyptian passion. Cleopatra, with her beauty and theatricality, draws him deeper into a world of sensuality, leading to his downfall.

What makes the play especially rich is Shakespeare's use of symbolic language. Erotic imagery, phallic symbols such as swords, yonic and fertility images are not simply decorative. They serve as central tools to explore the relationship between personal desire and political identity. Erotic power becomes political power and the subversion of sexual norms becomes a threat to Roman order.

This paper argues that Shakespeare employs a network of erotic and phallic symbols in *Antony and Cleopatra* to highlight gender fluidity, undermine patriarchal ideals and dramatises the tragic consequences of desire. The discussion will proceed in four parts. First, the erotic landscape of Egypt and Cleopatra's allure. Second, the phallic symbolism of swords and masculinity. Third, the role of yonic and fertility imagery and finally, the psycho-sexual subtleties of sadism, masochism and gender fluidity. Together, these symbolic layers reveal how the play critiques Roman ideals of masculinity, dramatises cultural anxieties and presents sexuality as forces capable of reshaping empires.

The Erotic Landscape: Cleopatra's Allure and the World of Egypt as a Feminine Space

The opening lines of the play, Shakespeare presents Egypt as a world dominated by sensuality and passion. Philo laments Antony's decline;

Those his goodly eyes,
That o'er the files and musters of the war
Have glow'd like plated Mars, now bend, now turn
The office and devotion of their view
Upon a tawny front. (Shakespeare 1.1.2–6)

Philo describes how Antony, once Mars-like in war, now gazes on Cleopatra's face, suggesting a fall from military greatness to erotic distraction. He continues;

His captain's heart,
Which in the scuffles of great fights hath burst
The buckles on his breast, reneges all temper,
And is become the bellows and the fan
To cool a gypsy's lust. (Shakespeare 1.1.6–10)

Here, Antony's heart, once a symbol of military courage and now serves only to fuel Cleopatra's desire. Rome sees this as shameful, presenting Egypt as a dangerous feminine force that weakens men.

Cleopatra as Erotic Power

Cleopatra herself embodies the erotic power of Egypt. She is described in hyperbolic and contradictory terms: a “gypsy,” a “strumpet,” a “serpent of old Nile,” but also a goddess-like figure associated with Venus. Enobarbus’s description of her arrival on the Cydnus river is one of the most famous passages in Shakespeare;

For her own person,
It beggar’d all description: she did lie
In her pavilion, cloth-of-gold, of tissue,
O’er picturing that Venus where we see
The fancy outwork nature. (Shakespeare 2.2.199–203)

Cleopatra’s beauty is said to surpass even that of Venus, the goddess of love, placing her beyond human description. Her theatrical entrance establishes her as a figure of irresistible erotic power.

Antony’s Surrender to Passion

Antony himself openly rejects Rome for Cleopatra;

Let Rome in Tiber melt, and the wide arch
Of the ranged empire fall! Here is my space. (Shakespeare 1.1.33–35)

This declaration shows his prioritisation of passion over empire. For Rome, this is dangerous: Antony abandons duty and threatens the stability of the empire. Shakespeare here dramatises a central tension of the play, the clash between reason and passion, duty and desire.

Cleopatra’s power is not passive. It is active and theatrical. She constantly tests Antony’s devotion, plays with his emotions and uses her sexuality as a tool of manipulation.

As Flore Chevallier argues, Cleopatra represents a “cultural and gender crisis,” disrupting Roman ideals of masculinity and authority (Chevallier 121).

Phallic Symbolism: Swords, Masculinity and Emasculation

In Roman culture, the sword represents masculine honour, military strength and political identity. Antony often refers to Caesar in terms of sword imagery, mocking him for weakness;

He at Philippi kept
His sword e’en like a dancer. (Shakespeare. 3.13.27–28)

Here, Antony dismisses Caesar’s masculinity, suggesting that a true Roman man proves himself “sword against sword” (Shakespeare 3.13.31). Timothy Grams observes that Roman masculinity in the play is always tied to “martial prowess and public honour” (Grams 45).

Cleopatra’s Subversion of the Sword

But Cleopatra destabilises this phallic symbol. She recalls a playful role reversal;

I drunk him to his bed,
Then put my tires and mantles on him, whilst
I wore his sword Philippan. (Shakespeare 2.5.21–23)

This scene reveals Cleopatra wears Antony’s sword while he wears her clothing. The act emasculates Antony and shows Cleopatra wielding masculine power. As Shmoop’s analysis suggests, this memory reflects Cleopatra’s pleasure in symbolically dominating Antony.

Antony’s Emasculation

Antony himself admits his weakness;

My sword, made weak by my affection, would
Obey it on all cause. (Shakespeare 3.11.67–69)

Here, he acknowledges that love for Cleopatra has weakened his masculine identity.

Caesar comments similarly;

You shall find thereempha
A man who is the abstract of all faults
That all men follow. (Shakespeare. 1.4.8–10)

Antony becomes “othered,” no longer fitting the Roman image of manhood. As Cleopatra appropriates the sword, Antony loses his symbolic power. This subversion of the phallic order represents a threat to Rome’s patriarchal system.

Yonic Imagery and Fertility Symbols

Cleopatra is linked with fertility and natural imagery. She is called the “serpent of old Nile,” suggesting both danger and life-giving power. Egypt itself, with the abundance of the Nile is portrayed as fertile and lush.

Enobarbus describes Antony and Cleopatra’s union with agricultural imagery: Antony “ploughs” while Cleopatra “crops,” presenting her as fertile soil. This aligns her with the natural world and motherhood.

The Monument as Yonic Symbol

Yet this fertility is inverted in the play’s ending. Cleopatra retreats to her “monument,” which becomes a yonic symbol of death rather than life;

Go tell him I have slain myself; say that

The last I spoke was, ‘Antony.’ (Shakespeare 4.13.11–12)

The monument is like a womb, but instead of giving birth, it houses death. Shakespeare transforms a symbol of life into one of containment and barrenness.

The Asp and Erotic Death

Cleopatra’s suicide with the asp also blends erotic and maternal imagery. She presses the asp to her breast;

With thy sharp teeth this knot intricate

Of life at once untie; poor venomous fool,

Be angry, and dispatch. (Shakespeare 5.2.301–303)

Later, she is described as if nursing the snake;

As sweet as balm, as soft as air, as gentle—

O Antony! Nay, I will take thee too. (Shakespeare 5.2.314–315)

The asp, called the “pretty worm of Nilus” (*Shakespeare. 5.2.246*), is both a phallic symbol and a creature of death. By nursing it, Cleopatra perverts maternal imagery feeding death instead of life. The Countryman even jokes with sexual double meanings: “the worm will do his kind” (*Shakespeare 5.2.261-262*).

Cleopatra’s death, then is an eroticized union with death itself and a final act of self-possession. By choosing death, she denies Caesar the power to parade her as a trophy. Shakespeare deliberately leaves out Cleopatra’s children (who appear in Plutarch) to emphasise

her political identity rather than her maternal role. As Chevallier analyses, Cleopatra embodies a “public female figure” who resists being confined to private domesticity (Chevallier 124).

Psycho-Sexual Dynamics: Sadism, Masochism and Gender Fluidity Antony's Masochism

Antony's relationship with Cleopatra can be understood in psycho-sexual terms. He repeatedly accepts humiliation from her, showing a kind of masochistic pleasure. Vogel argues that Antony experiences a “masochistic fetishism,” finding joy in his submission to Cleopatra (Vogel 25).

When Cleopatra mocks him about Fulvia's death or his failures, Antony does not react with anger. Instead, he continues to adore her. His final embrace of death is framed as a wedding;

I will be bridegroom in my death
priorit run into't
As to a lover's bed. (Shakespeare 4.15.99–101)

This line suggests that Antony treats death as a sexual consummation, a masochistic union with Cleopatra and with the end itself.

Cleopatra's Sadism

Cleopatra, on the other hand, plays the sadistic role. She manipulates Antony emotionally. On many occasions she tests his loyalty and mocks his masculinity. Her power comes not just from beauty but from her ability to dominate him psychologically.

This sadomasochistic dynamic reflects the larger power struggle between Rome and Egypt. Rome should be dominant, but Egypt, embodied in Cleopatra, dominates through erotic and psychological power.

Gender Fluidity

Cleopatra's adoption of masculine symbols like the sword, the fishing hook and Antony's acceptance of submissive roles blur gender boundaries. As Vogel notes, their relationship allows for "fluidity of gender roles" (Vogel 26). This challenges the binary opposition of male and female.

However, while this fluidity is liberating in their private relationship, it cannot survive in the political world of Rome. Rome demands rigid masculinity and Antony's failure to uphold it leads to his downfall. Shakespeare thus presents a paradox, love allows Antony to expand his identity, but that very expansion destroys him in a world that cannot accept gender fluidity.

Conclusion

Shakespeare's *Antony and Cleopatra* uses erotic and phallic symbolism to explore the tension between desire and duty, passion and politics, masculinity and femininity. Cleopatra's allure and theatricality undermine Antony's Roman honour, while swords and phallic symbols highlight his emasculation. Yonic symbols link Cleopatra to fertility and Egypt's abundance, but they are tragically inverted in her death, where life becomes death and motherhood becomes perversion.

The sadomasochistic dynamics between Antony and Cleopatra reflect larger cultural anxieties. Rome's fear of feminine power and Egypt's challenge to Roman masculinity. Their love reveals the fragility of rigid gender norms and the instability of cultural identity.

Ultimately, Shakespeare suggests that sexuality is not separate from politics but deeply entwined with it. Desire can reshape empires, redefine identities and overturn social orders.

Cleopatra, with her “infinite variety,” remains an enduring symbol of erotic power, while Antony stands as a tragic figure undone by his inability to balance passion with duty.

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